

Supporting Information

Tunable bidirectional electroosmotic flow for diffusion-based separation

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Table of Contents

- S1. Material and methods
 - S1.1. Experimental visualization
 - S1.2. Device fabrication
 - S1.3. Experimental setup and procedure
- S2. Analytical model of the BFF
 - S2.1. Taylor-Aris dispersion derivation
 - S2.2. Separation purity
- S3. Generating bidirectional flow
- S4. Monte Carlo simulation of the separation
- S5. BFF using chemical patterning
- Captions for movies S1 to S4

S1. Material and methods

S1.1. Experimental visualization

We visualized all the experiments with an upright fluorescence microscope (AZ100, Nikon) using a LED light source (Sola, Lumencor), and a 5x objective (AZ-Plan Fluor 5×, Nikon,). We used 1 μm-diameter pink carboxyl particles (Spherotech Inc.) to demonstrate separation from rhodamine B (Sigma-Aldrich) (Fig. 1c) and to trace the flow (Fig. 4). The beads and dye were imaged using a TRITC filter (Nikon, 525/40 excitation, 605/55 emission, and 565 nm dichroic mirror). For the separation of antibodies from dye (Fig. 6), we used FITC-conjugated goat anti-rabbit IgG antibodies (Jackson ImmunoResearch Labs Inc.) and Alexa fluor 555 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) imaged using a FITC filter (Nikon, 465/95 excitation, 515/55 emission, and 505 nm dichroic mirror) and a TRITC filter, respectively. All the experiments were imaged using an sCMOS camera (Zyla 4.2 sCMOS, Andor) with a 100 ms exposure time.

S1.2. Device fabrication

Fig. S1 shows schematics of the fabrication steps. Complete details of the fabrication process can be found in our previous work^[1]. Briefly, we deposit a layer of 2 nm Pt sandwiched between two layers of 2 nm Ti on a borosilicate glass wafer, and define the metal structures (driving, ground, gate electrodes, and resistor array) by a lift-off process. Then, we deposit a dielectric composed of 500 nm SiON followed by 100 nm of SiO₂ by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD). We open the electrical connection (driving, ground, and pads electrode) by buffered hydrofluoric acid (BHF) etching of the dielectric. To define the microfluidic channels, we spin-coat and pattern a 15-μm-thick layer of SU-8

photoresist on top of the wafer. Finally, we dice the wafer, and bond each device to a flat piece of PDMS with punched holes for fluidic inlets and outlets.

Fig. S1 Illustration of the electrode array device fabrication steps. (1) We deposit and define the metal structures (2nm Ti/2nm Pt/ 2nmTi) by lift-off process. (2) We deposit the dielectric (500 nm SiON + 100 nm SiO₂), and (3) open the electrical connections (driving, ground electrode and pads) by etching. (4) We spin-coat and pattern a 15 μm -thick SU8 photoresist to define the microfluidics chamber, and (5) cover the chamber with a PDMS slab with punched holes for the reservoirs.

S1.3. Experimental setup and procedures

Fig. S2 shows a photograph of the experimental setup used in all experiments. We mounted the device on a homemade connector fixed on the stage of an upright fluorescent microscope (AZ100, Nikon, Tokyo, Japan). The connector is composed of a 3D printed part and a PCB containing electrical pins. Using these pins, we connected the external resistors R_{ext} (variable resistor, Bourns) and the power supplies (Keithley 2410, Tektronix) with the device. We used the output of a pulse generator (Stanford research systems, DG535) and an in-house MATLAB code (R2018b, Mathworks) to trigger simultaneously the power supplies such that they provide square-wave signals with a frequency of 25 Hz.

At the beginning of each experiment, we first filled the channel with ethanol, then with DI, and finally with an aqueous buffer. We loaded the sample containing the species onto the left reservoir prior to the separation. At the end of the experiment, we cleaned the device by flowing consecutively acetone, ethanol, and DI and dried it by applying a negative pressure to one of the reservoirs. This allowed re-using the same device for multiple experiments.

Fig. S2 Image of the experimental setup. The device is mounted on a homemade connector composed of a 3D printed holder and a PCB containing spring-loaded contacts (pogo pin). This assembly is placed under the objective of an upright fluorescent microscope. The power supplies (not shown) and the external resistors (R_{ext}) are connected with the device via the pins on the connector.

S2. Analytical model of the BFF

S2.1. Taylor-Aris dispersion derivation

As shown in Fig. S3, we consider the case of a microfluidic chamber of length L , height h , and width $2w$, filled with a liquid subjected to an imposed flow field $u(y)$, and in fluidic connection with two reservoirs. The left reservoir (inlet) contains a chemical species of diffusivity D at a constant concentration c_0 . Under the lubrication approximation, $h \ll L$, the concentration distribution c of the species in the chamber is described by the advection-diffusion equation

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + u(y) \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = D \left(\frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial y^2} \right), \quad (\text{S1})$$

subjected to a no-flux boundary condition $\partial c / \partial y (y = \pm w) = 0$ at the side walls of the chamber and $c(x=0, t > 0) = c_0$ at the chamber inlet. Away from the inlet/outlet, we consider a bidirectional flow with a velocity profile $u(y) = U \operatorname{erf}(by) + U_b$, where erf is the error function, b is a coefficient describing the steepness of the velocity gradient, U is its amplitude, and U_b is a bias in the average flow velocity. When

$b \rightarrow \infty$, $u(y)$ becomes a step function with a flow velocity of $-U + U_b$ in the upper stripe, and $U + U_b$ in the lower stripe.

Following Stone and Brenner's approach^[2] for Taylor-Aris dispersion analysis^[3], we define an average operator as $\langle f \rangle = (2w)^{-1} \int_{-w}^w f dy$ and we express c and u as a sum of their average and a perturbation term,

$$c(x, y, t) = \langle c(x, t) \rangle + c'(x, y, t), \quad (\text{S2})$$

$$u(y) = \langle u(y) \rangle + u'(y), \quad (\text{S3})$$

where $\langle u(y) \rangle = U_b$ and $u'(y) = Uerf(by)$. The no-flux boundary conditions become $\partial c' / \partial y (y = \pm w) = 0$.

Substituting Eqs. S2 and S3 in Eq. S1, and applying the average operator $\langle \cdot \rangle$, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \langle c \rangle}{\partial t} + \langle u \rangle \frac{\partial \langle c \rangle}{\partial x} + \left\langle u' \frac{\partial c'}{\partial x} \right\rangle = D \frac{\partial^2 \langle c \rangle}{\partial x^2}, \quad (\text{S4})$$

in which the term $\langle u' (\partial c' / \partial x) \rangle$ is still unknown. We subtract Eq. S4 from Eq. S1, and obtain

$$\frac{\partial c'}{\partial t} + u' \frac{\partial \langle c \rangle}{\partial x} + \langle u \rangle \frac{\partial c'}{\partial x} + u' \frac{\partial c'}{\partial x} = D \left(\frac{\partial^2 c'}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 c'}{\partial y^2} \right) + \left\langle u' \frac{\partial c'}{\partial x} \right\rangle \quad (\text{S5})$$

Denoting with the $\hat{\cdot}$ symbol non-dimensional quantities, we perform the following scaling:

$$\langle c \rangle = c_0 \langle \hat{c} \rangle, \quad c' = c'_0 \hat{c}', \quad y = w \hat{y}, \quad x = L_{ob} \hat{x}, \quad t = t_0 \hat{t}, \quad \langle u \rangle = U \langle \hat{u} \rangle, \quad u' = U \hat{u}' \quad (\text{S6})$$

where L_{ob} is the distance from the inlet at which we choose to observe the concentration, and $t_0 = L_{ob}/U$ is the associated advection time scale. We consider a time scale much longer than the characteristic time scale associated with lateral diffusion, $L_{ob}/U \gg w^2/D$, i.e. $w^2 U / D L_{ob} \sim O(\varepsilon) \ll 1$; further, we assume that the quantities c'_0/c_0 and w^2/L_{ob}^2 are also of order ε . Using these scaling arguments, we consider the leading order contributions, i.e. order ε , of Eq. S4 obtaining

$$u' \frac{\partial \langle c \rangle}{\partial x} = D \frac{\partial^2 c'}{\partial y^2}. \quad (\text{S7})$$

Fig. S3 Schematic of the analyzed configuration.

We solve for c' by integrating Eq. S7 twice with respect to y , obtaining

$$c'(x, y) = \frac{\partial \langle c \rangle}{\partial x} \frac{U}{D} \left[\frac{\left(2(by)^2 + 1 \right) \operatorname{erf}(by) + \frac{2bye^{-(by)^2}}{\sqrt{\pi}}}{4b^2} \right] + C_1 y + C_2, \quad (\text{S8})$$

where

$$C_1 = \left. \frac{\partial c'}{\partial y} \right|_{y=-w} = \left. \frac{\partial c'}{\partial y} \right|_{y=w} = -\frac{\partial \langle c \rangle}{\partial x} \frac{U}{D} \left(w \cdot \operatorname{erf}(bw) + \frac{e^{-(bw)^2}}{\sqrt{\pi}b} \right), \quad (\text{S9})$$

$$C_2 = c'(x, y = 0), \quad (\text{S10})$$

are constants associated with the boundary and initial conditions. The term $\langle u'(\partial c'/\partial x) \rangle$ can be calculated using the solution for c' , i.e. Eq. S8,

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle u' \frac{\partial c'}{\partial x} \right\rangle &= \frac{\partial^2 \langle c \rangle}{\partial x^2} \frac{U^2}{2wD} \int_{-w}^w \operatorname{erf}(by) \cdot \overbrace{\left(\frac{\left(2(by)^2 + 1 \right) \operatorname{erf}(by) + \frac{2bye^{-(by)^2}}{\sqrt{\pi}}}{4b^2} \right)}^{I_1} dy \\ &\quad + \frac{U}{2w} \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial x} \int_{-w}^w \operatorname{erf}(by) \cdot y dy, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S11})$$

and solving for the two integrals I_1 and I_2 for $b \rightarrow \infty$

$$I_1 = \frac{\partial^2 \langle c \rangle}{\partial x^2} \frac{U^2 w^2}{6D}, \quad (\text{S12})$$

$$I_2 = -\frac{\partial^2 \langle c \rangle}{\partial x^2} \frac{U^2 w^2}{2D}. \quad (\text{S13})$$

Finally, we use this result to calculate the term $\langle u'(\partial c'/\partial x) \rangle$ as

$$\left\langle u' \frac{\partial c'}{\partial x} \right\rangle = I_1 + I_2 = -\frac{D}{3} \frac{\partial^2 \langle c \rangle}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{Uw}{D} \right)^2. \quad (\text{S14})$$

By substituting Eq. S14 in Eq. S4 and re-arranging the terms, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \langle c \rangle}{\partial t} + \langle u \rangle \frac{\partial \langle c \rangle}{\partial x} = D \left(1 + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{Uw}{D} \right)^2 \right) \frac{\partial^2 \langle c \rangle}{\partial x^2}, \quad (\text{S15})$$

which is a diffusion-advection equation with a constant advective term $\langle u \rangle = U_b$ and an effective diffusion coefficient $D_{eff} = D \left(1 + \frac{1}{3} Pe_w^2 \right)$, where $Pe_w = Uw/D$ is the lateral Péclet number. The solution of this equation for $\langle c \rangle$, with a no-flux boundary condition $\partial c / \partial y (y = \pm w) = 0$ at the side walls of the chamber and $c(x=0, t > 0) = c_0$, is^[4]

$$\langle c \rangle = \frac{c_0}{2} \left(\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x - U_b t}{2\sqrt{D_{eff} t}} \right) + e^{\frac{U_b x}{D_{eff}}} \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x + U_b t}{2\sqrt{D_{eff} t}} \right) \right). \quad (\text{S16})$$

In case of unbiased bidirectional flow field, i.e. $U_b = 0$, the solution of Eq. S16 reduces to

$$\langle c \rangle = c_0 \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{D_{eff} t}} \right). \quad (\text{S17})$$

S2.2. Separation purity

Considering two different species, one with a lower diffusivity (denoted hereafter by a subscript *LD*), and one with a higher diffusivity (denoted by a subscript *HD*), we define the purity of the separation as the ratio of area-averaged concentration of species *i*, to the sum of area-averaged concentrations of all species at a given axial location and at given time,

$$P(x, t) = \frac{\langle c_{LD}(x, t) \rangle}{\langle c_{LD}(x, t) \rangle + \langle c_{HD}(x, t) \rangle}. \quad (\text{S18})$$

Fig. 2 in the manuscript shows the theoretical purity values as a function of the diffusivities of two species and given set of system parameters (U , w , t , L). Here we show that for a given specific pair of species, the purity can be tuned and optimized by changing the system parameters, such as the strip width w and velocity U . Fig. S4A shows the purity for the separation of IgA antibody ($D = 5.2 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) from 67 kDa protein ($D = 7.2 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$), as a function of U and w . For example for $U = 40 \text{ } \mu\text{m/s}$ and $w = 100 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ (point A), the purity is approximately 60 %, but by changing the width to $20 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, the purity can be increased to 98% (point B). A similar analysis can be conducted for different separation problems based on the diffusivities of the species of interest.

The penetration length describes a balance between axial advection and lateral diffusion, however, due to axial diffusion, the concentration profile of any species with a penetration length within the chamber can

never reach a steady state and a diffusive front slowly propagates toward the right reservoir. As a result, the purity is also a (decreasing) function of time. This decrease of the purity with time can be however easily countered by establishing a non-symmetric flow profile wherein the flow velocity of the returning flow strips is higher than that of the outgoing flow strips. Fig. S4B shows the purity for cells-proteins separation as a function of time, for different ratios between the returning and outgoing velocity (defined as β). These results indicate that increasing the returning velocity gradually improves the purity, and for a difference in flow velocities higher than three, the purity is maintained above 90% over long durations of time.

Fig. S4 Analytical results showing the purity P of a separation. (A) The purity for the separation of IgA from a 67 kDa protein as a function of U and w . For a given velocity of $40 \mu\text{m/s}$, by changing strip width from $100 \mu\text{m}$ (point A) to $20 \mu\text{m}$ (point B), the purity can be improved by 55 %. (B) The purity for the separation of cells from proteins, as a function of time for two velocity profiles. For a symmetric velocity profile ($\beta=1$), P reduces with time due to axial diffusion. An asymmetric profile where the returning velocity is three times higher than the outgoing velocity allows maintaining a high-purity over a longer time. For all the plots, we set $U_1 = 40 \mu\text{m/s}$ and $U_2 = \beta U_1$.

S3. Generating bidirectional flow

In this section, we present details of the design of the electronic circuit and the gate electrode array shown in Fig. S5A. To achieve strips of uniform flow, the zeta potential of all electrodes in a given row must be uniform. However, as illustrated in Fig. S5B since the bulk potential is non-uniform, each electrode must be assigned a different absolute voltage value. We ground the electrode in the right reservoir and set the voltage in the left reservoir to a square-wave with frequency ω and amplitude ϕ , i.e. $V(t) = \phi f(\omega t)$, where f is a square-wave function. Consequently, the bulk potential distribution in the chamber is $V_{ch}(x, t) = (L - x)V(t) / L = (1 - x / L)\phi f(\omega t)$. Defining $\phi_{ch}(x) = (1 - x / L)\phi$, the bulk potential can be compactly written as $V_{ch}(x, t) = \phi_{ch}(x)f(\omega t)$. Assuming that each gate electrode is actuated with the same waveform but with its own amplitude, $V_{el,i} = \phi_{el,i}f(\omega t)$, where i is the index number of the electrode ($i=1 \dots N$), the induced zeta potential ζ_i of the i -th electrode in a row is given by

$$\zeta_i = \zeta_0 + \frac{\lambda_{EDL} \epsilon_d}{d \epsilon_i} \Delta \phi_i. \quad (\text{S19})$$

where ζ_0 is the native zeta potential of the surface, λ_{EDL} is the thickness of the electric double layer, and $\Delta \phi_i = \phi_{el,i} - \phi_{ch,i}$ is the difference between the potential assigned to the gate electrode and the potential in the chamber in the vicinity of the i -electrode, $\phi_{ch,i}(x) = \phi_{ch}(x = i\Delta x) = (1 - i\Delta x / L)\phi$.

To achieve uniform zeta potential and flow in each row with index number r , $\Delta \phi_i$ must be constant along the row, $\Delta \phi_i = \Delta \phi^{(r)}$. Each row of electrodes must thus have an additional bias $\Delta \phi^{(r)}$ on top of the driving potential $\phi_{ch,i}$ in the vicinity of the electrode. Fig. S5A presents the electrical circuit we use to achieve this potential distribution. For each row, an additional power supply is connected in series with V , providing the required bias $\Delta \phi^{(r)}$. We use a series of identical resistors, implemented by long connection lines on the chip, each with a resistance R to form a voltage divider. For a given resistance R , the correct voltage drop across each resistor would be obtained only for a precise electric current. To control the total electric current in the system, we use one additional resistor for each row $R_{ext}^{(r)}$, which we implement using an external (off-chip) variable resistor connected to the voltage divider. From Kirchoff's law, we obtained the required value of $R_{ext}^{(r)}$,

$$R_{ext}^{(r)} = \frac{|\Delta \phi^{(r)}|}{\phi} (N - 1)R. \quad (\text{S20})$$

The value of the resistors should be as high as possible so that the electric current in the system is minimal, thus avoiding undesired heating. Due to limited space on chip, the maximally available area for each resistor R is approximately $800 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$, resulting in a typical value of $20 \text{ k}\Omega$. While for a generic bidirectional flow, each row of electrode requires its own external resistor, for bidirectional flow with an average zero velocity we need only two external resistors and we set $\Delta\phi^{(1)} = -\Delta\phi^{(2)} = \Delta\phi$, because multiple rows sharing the same velocity can be grouped by interconnecting electrode rows at the chip level. Fig. S6 shows a schematic of such a device with four rows of gate electrodes.

Fig. S5 Generation of bidirectional electroosmotic flow using AC-FEEO. (A) Illustration of the device composed of a microfluidic chamber with driving and ground electrode in the reservoir, an array of gate electrodes, a network of resistors ($R, R_{ext}^{(1)}, R_{ext}^{(2)}$) and three voltage power supplies. (B) The voltage supplies provide a square-wave potential at frequency ω , and as a result, the voltage across the chamber decreases during the first half period ($0 < t < T$), and increases during the second half period ($T < t < 2T$). The network of resistors sets the potential of the gate electrodes in one row, such that the difference between the bulk and gate potential $\Delta\phi$ is kept constant. As a result, the EOF (white arrows) in row of gate electrodes has constant direction and magnitude.

Fig. S6 Design layout of a simplified four-row electrode array in which the electrodes of alternated rows (in each column) are interconnected. This simplifies the external circuitry, as alternated rows share the same external resistor, but allows only two velocities to be implemented at any given time.

S4. Monte Carlo simulation of the separation

A simple and straightforward method to investigate the behaviour of particles placed in a 2D bidirectional flow is through a Monte Carlo simulation. Fig. S7 shows results of the simulation of separation of two species ($D_{\text{red}} = 0.1 \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, $D_{\text{green}} = 50 \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$) using flow strips with width $w = 50 \mu\text{m}$, and absolute flow velocity in each of the strip of $U = 30 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$. We use MATLAB to calculate the displacement of individual particles at each time step as a superposition of their advective displacement due to the bidirectional flow, and their brownian motion. To simulate a continuous injection from the left reservoir, at each time step we create 20 new particles at $x=0$, equally distributed along the y -axis. We choose a time step of $\Delta t = w^2 / (D_{\text{green}} \cdot 100) = 0.5\text{s}$ to allow sufficient sampling within a characteristic diffusion time between strips. At each time step we displace each of the particles by the sum of two displacement: (1) a deterministic axial displacement of $u(y) \cdot \Delta t$, where $u(y)$ is the local axial velocity of the particle according to its location, and (2) a random displacement in both x and y , according to a normal distribution with zero mean and a standard deviation of $\sqrt{2Dt}$ (in each of the axes). Similar to the analytical model and the experimental results, the Monte Carlo simulations predict well the penetration length as a function of the system parameters.

Fig. S7 Monte Carlo simulation of separation of different species ($D_{red} = 0.1 \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, $D_{green} = 50 \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$) at two different times (30 s and 200 s), and using flow strips with width $w = 50 \mu\text{m}$, and absolute flow velocity in each of the strip of $U = 30 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$. A time-lapse video showing the simulation is provided in SI Movie S3.

S5. BFF using chemical patterning

Fabrication and demonstration

Instead of using AC-FEEO and gate electrodes array as discussed in the main text, bidirectional electroosmotic flows could be also achieved by chemical patterning. Following our previous work^[5], we modify the zeta-potential by depositing stripes of a positive polymer, poly(allylamine hydrochloride) (PAH), onto a negative glass substrate. To create the stripes pattern, we prepare a set of parallel channels in PDMS using standard lithography techniques, and use them to flow $1 \mu\text{M}$ PAH in a buffer containing 100mM tris, 50 mM HCl and 100 mM NaCl (pH = 8.2) for 5 minutes over the glass surface. We then remove the channels, rinse the glass with DI and dry it using nitrogen gas. As shown in Fig. S8a, the patterned glass then serves as the floor of the microfluidic chamber which we close with 1.5 cm-long, 3 mm-wide and $15 \mu\text{m}$ -deep PDMS chamber treated with PLL-PEG (poly(L-lysine) randomly grafted

with poly(ethylene glycol) side-chains) to minimize its zeta potential, and thus its contribution to the EOF^[5].

Fig. S8b-c shows experimental results of separation of 1- μm neutral beads from rhodamine B in the BFF using 5 mM bistris and 2.5 mM HCl (pH 6.5) buffer and a 16 V/cm DC field parallel to the stripes. Both species are placed in the left reservoir and enter the chamber by the streamlines leading to the right reservoir. The dye rapidly diffuses between streamlines resulting in a dispersed yet stationary front, whereas the beads remain on their individual streamlines and are advected towards the right reservoir.

Fig. S8 Experimental setup and demonstrating separation of neutral low-diffusivity 1- μm beads ($D = 4.1 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) from a neutral high diffusivity dye, rhodamine B ($D = 4.2 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$). **a.** Schematic of the device composed of a microfluidic chamber, substrate patterned with stripes of different zeta potential, and electrodes in the reservoirs to drive a DC electric field. **b.** Rhodamine B is placed in the left reservoir (not shown) and upon the application of an external electric field is pulled in the channel by the EOF over the native glass stripes and is pushed back by the PAH coated stripes, resulting in a stationary front. **c.** Neutral (PLL-PEG coated) 1 μm fluorescent beads are spiked in the left reservoir and are carried towards the left by the EOF generated on the native glass stripes. The experiments were carried out at field strength of $\sim 16 \text{ V/cm}$ using a buffer composition of 5 mM bistris and 2.5 mM HCl (pH 6.5). A time-lapse video showing the separation is provided in SI Movie S4.

In contrast to AC-FEEO, this approach works only with DC electric fields, because the zeta potential patterns on the substrate are fixed. In addition, the value of the zeta potential depends on the chemical coatings and the pH value of the solution, and cannot be tuned dynamically, thus the magnitude of the bidirectional flow velocity can be modified only by changing the electric field. While separation of charged species could also be achieved, the additional motion of each species due to its own electromigration must be accounted for as part of its drift velocity.

pH dependence

Because zeta potential and EOF wall mobility strongly depend on the pH of the buffer, characterization of the EOF as a function of the pH is essential for testing its applicability for biological applications which require a specific and narrow pH range.

Fig. S9 shows the electroosmotic (EO) mobility of native and PAH-coated glass as a function of the pH of the solution in the range 3.0 to 9.7 and at ionic strength of approximately 25 mM (buffer compositions provided in Table S2). All the experiments were performed out at electric field strength of 50 V/cm. The electroosmotic mobilities were measured by monitoring the migration velocity of fluorescent tracer particles on a glass slide uniformly coated with 1 μM PAH. To eliminate the electrophoretic migration of the tracer, we used neutral particles. For this we coated 1- μm beads with PLL-PEG dissolved in hepes/NaOH buffer (pH 7.4 and ionic strength \sim 5 mM) following the protocol described in our previous work^[5]. The beads were visualized with an inverted epi-fluorescent microscope and imaged using a camera with an exposure time of 1 s. The average velocity of the beads was calculated from monitoring at least 9 beads, and the experiment were repeated three times. The strongest contrast is obtained between pH 4.5 and 7.5, where both surfaces present EO mobilities similar in magnitude an opposite in sign. In addition, this range is compatible with most biological samples. Therefore, we choose a buffer composed of bistris/HCl (pH 6.5) to perform to generate the bidirectional flow and perform the separation experiment.

Fig. S9 Measurements of the electroosmotic mobility of native glass (dashed lines) and PAH coated glass (solid lines) as a function of pH of the solution. The optimal working pH range for generating bidirectional flows is between 4.5 and 7.5, where the absolute value of EOF of both surfaces is maximized. The electroosmotic mobilities were measured by monitoring the migration velocity of nearly neutral PEGylated 1- μm beads subjected to a 50 V/cm electric field.

Table S2. Composition of the buffer solutions used for the characterization of the electroosmotic mobility of native glass and PAH coated glass in function of pH.

Buffer	pH	Ionic strength (mM)	Conductance (S/m)	Buffer capacity (mM)
50 mM citric / 25 mM NaOH	3.059	26.7	0.206	34.5
50 mM lactic/ 25 mM NaOH	3.8	25	0.194	29.2
50 mM acetic/25 mM NaOH	4.694	25	0.202	28.8
50 mM MES/ 25 mM NaOH	6.032	25	0.168	28.7
50 mM bistris/ 25mM HCl	6.463	25	0.176	29.6
50 mM HEPES/ 25 mM NaOH	7.437	25	0.157	28.7
50 mM tris/ 25 mM HCl	8.139	25	0.184	29.6
50 mM glycine / 25 mM NaOH	9.715	25	0.191	28.9

Captions for movies

Movie S1. Separation of beads from dye using gate electrodes. Fluorescence raw data time-lapse showing separation of 1- μm beads from dye in a BFF device composed of two rows of gate electrodes. The video is taken near the left reservoir, where the separation of the two species can be visualized within the same field of view.

Movie S2. Generating bidirectional flow. An array of four rows of gate electrodes gives rise to a bidirectional electroosmotic flow field in a microfluidic chamber. The video shows a fluorescence raw data time lapse of 1 μm -diameter fluorescent beads moving under the flow field.

Movie S3. Monte Carlo simulation of separation. Monte Carlo simulation showing the separation of two species ($D_{\text{red}} = 0.1 \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, $D_{\text{green}} = 50 \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$) using flow strips with width $w = 50 \mu\text{m}$, and absolute flow velocity of $U = 30 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$.

Movie S4. Separation of beads from dye using chemical patterning. Bidirectional EOF can be also achieved by chemically patterning the floor of the microfluidic chamber with strips of opposite zeta potential. The video shows a fluorescence raw data time-lapse showing separation of beads from dye in such device.

References

- [1] F. Paratore, V. Bacheva, G. V. Kaigala, M. Bercovici, *PNAS* **2019**, 201821269.
- [2] H. A. Stone, H. Brenner, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **1999**, 38, 851–854.
- [3] Aris R., Taylor Geoffrey Ingram, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences* **1956**, 235, 67–77.
- [4] Akio Ogata, Banks, *A Solution of the Differential Equation of Longitudinal Disperison in Porous Media*, **1961**.
- [5] F. Paratore, E. Boyko, G. V. Kaigala, M. Bercovici, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2019**, 122, 224502.